

doi:10.5281/zenodo.18344095

Effect Of Organised Criminal Groups Activities And Social Life In Nasarawa State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

An organised criminal group refers to a group that would likely encourage its members, including members of its sub-group to collectively or frequently engage in violent illegal act. They operate in well organised transnational, national or local groups and cooperate to carry out coordinated illegal actions that are diver stating to human being and social life in general. The groups typically involve certain hierarchies and are headed by one or several powerful leader(s). The group activities if not checked and control will lead to total collapse of society and its environs. The study basically made use of secondary data to examine the effects of organised criminal groups' activities on social life in Nasarawa State, Nigeria. Three groups was put together to constitute organised criminal group, these are banditry, Boko Haram and Fulani militia. At the end of the study it was discovered that social life was affected by organised criminal groups' activities in the state. The study recommended that the ugly scenario need to be checked, government should address the root factors that give birth to organised criminal groups, government should beef up security to control the activities of organized criminal groups, the welfare of citizens should be taken seriously to discourage people from forming and joining organised criminal groups. Politician should stop hiring youths to use them as thugs for their selfish gain in the society.

Keywords: effects, organised crime, organised crime group and social life

INTRODUCTION

Crime is one of the contending problems ravaging the human world today. It is however not a new phenomenon. Mankind has battled with both crime causative factors and control in order to curb its consequences for a long time. However as civilization evolves, crime of new dimension begin to emerge with diverse implications on the society.

Historically, the notion of crime denotes what is wrong or seen as a sin. The war against crime was presented on the notion of "lex talionis": an eye for an eye. Harsh penalties were used. The law of Hammurabi adopted a retributive approach against criminals and demanded that a criminal suffers in like degree with the suffering he had caused.

Similarly, the Mosaic Code, which placed emphasis on retaliation, saw crime as a sin that must be severely punished. In spite of these early laws, crime and criminality proliferated such that by late 18th century, scholars like Cesare Beccaria (1738-1794) and Jeremy Bethem (1748-1832) had began to advocate for law reforms that can deter crime and rehabilitate offenders. In his philosophical doctrine

of utilitarianism, Beccaria (1764) called for punishment based on its usefulness and practicality, a punishment that could be shift and certain; and punishment that can prevent crime through deterrence. In Europe and Britain, where the classical scholars used theories to justify the need for reforms to curb crime, Empirical studies reveal the emergence of new crime from mere theft to robbery, rape to gang raping of innocence women and from lone masked criminals to bare faced criminals with sophisticated weapons.

The extent to which any pervasive organised crime networks actually existed in eighteenth century Britain is debatable. Once illegal markets are accessed for the disposal of stolen goods, such criminal activity becomes inherently organised. However, it would take the modernizing aspects of society for more recognizable models of organised crime to evolve; the creation and circulation of financial instruments, new technologies in firearms, safes and transport infrastructures; the development of a strong surveillance culture that legislated the “habitual criminal” into being; the growth of global networks via colonialism; and the creation of the “underworld” in texts and literatures that could be accessed by a wide range of readers Shore, (2015).

Nigeria has been plaque by a number of insecurity issues, arising from different militia groups these include the militant groups formed in the Niger- Delta region to protest exploitation and environmental degradation due to oil exploration, the Boko Haram insurgency in the North Eastern part of the country, the Fulani militia group that is spread like wild fire across the country to mention but few. All these have been posing a variety of security threats to the country.

No state in the country is immune from the activities of organised criminal gang. For instance, Zamfara State has become a centre of Bandits in the North western region, while kidnapping which started in the south-south region is now widely practiced in the Northern States of Niger and Kaduna. Nasarawa State is having her fair share of organised criminal activities.

However, it is on these notes that this paper deem it fit to look at the effect of organized criminal groups’ activities on social life in Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

CONCEPTUAL CLEARIFICATION

Effects: These are consequences associated with the action of organised criminal gang.

Organised Crime: This is a criminal activity that are planned and controlled by powerful groups and carried out on a large scale. It is a category of transnational, national, or local groupings of highly centralized enterprises run by criminals to engage in illegal activity, most commonly for profit

Organised Crime Group: Means a group that would likely encourage its members, including members of its sub-group to collectively or frequently engage in violent illegal act. They operate in well organised transnational, national or local groups and cooperate to carry out coordinated illegal action. The groups typically involve certain hierarchies and are headed by one or several powerful leader(s).

Social life: refers to the interactions and relationships we have with others in our community, workplace or social circle such as religion worship centre, school, and marketplace

There are so many types of organised criminal groups in Nigeria namely: Banditry, Boko Haram, Fulani herdsmen militia, Niger Delta Militants, cult groups, cyber crime group, trafficking groups, pirates and oil bunkering, political thugs and so on and so forth.

However, the groups consider in this paper are Banditry; Boko Haram and Fulani Militia.

Banditry

Conceptually, banditry is a derivative of the term bandit meaning an unlawful armed group terrorizing people and confiscating their properties. It is synonymous with the establishment of gang groups who use small and light weapons to carry out attacks against people. In this regard, banditry could mean a set-up criminal activity deliberately designed and carried out for personal gains. Due to the complex nature of bandits' activities, Egwu (2016) in a restricted manner, described banditry as a practice of stealing cattle and animals from herders or raiding of cattle from their ranches. In the same vein, banditry is reflected in criminal escapades like cattle rustling, kidnapping, armed robbery, drug abuse,

arson, rape and the brazen and gruesome massacre of people of agrarian communities with sophisticated weapons by suspected herdsmen and reprisal attacks from surviving victims, a development that has been brought to the front burner of national security (Uche & Iwuamadi, 2018). In his perception, Shalangwa (2013) regards banditry as the practice of raiding and attacking victims by members of an armed group, whether or not premeditated, using weapons of offence or defense, especially in semi-organized groups for the purpose of overpowering the victim and obtaining loot or achieving some political goals. Such bandits are usually perceived as outlaws, desperate and lawless marauders who do not have a definite residence or destination but roam around the forest and mountains to avoid being identified, detected and arrested. However, where the term banditry is connected to rural, it implies a group of rural outlawed involved in illicit activities such as raiding of villages, kidnappings and cattle rustling for primitive accumulation of wealth. Thus, bandits are gang groups terrorizing and dispossessing local people or travelers of their valuable items or properties such as merchandise, money, cattle, camel, and sheep, among others. They operate within and along rural borders with the assistance of their local collaborators including in some cases, state agents deployed to work for the safety and security of the people (Abdullahi, 2019).

In another sense, banditry refers to the incidences of armed robbery or allied violent crimes, such as kidnapping, cattle rustling, and village or market raids. It involves the use of force, or threat to that effect, to intimidate a person or a group of persons in order to rob, rape or kill (Okoli & Okpaleke 2014). Economic or political interests motivate banditry. The former refers to banditries motivated by the imperative of material accumulation while the latter has to do with those driven by the quest to rob, to assault or to liquidate a person or a group of persons based on political or ideological dispositions (Okoli & Ugwu, 2019).

Thus banditry, in the context of this study, is defined as the totality of incidences of armed robbery or allied violent crimes, such as kidnapping, abduction, village raids as well as highway raids which involves the use of force, or threat to that effect, to intimidate a person or a group of persons in order to rob, rape, kidnap or kill the victims.

Boko Haram

‘Boko Haram is derived from a combination of two words, “Boko” and “Haram” The word “Boko” Is a native Hausa word, originally meaning sham, fraud, in authenticity, and such which came to represent Western education and learning. (Liman, 1968). Hence, ‘Boko’ came to symbolize Western education or Westernization, while ‘Haram’, according to the Merriam-Webster dictionary is an Arabic word which means ‘forbidden’, ‘ungodly’ or ‘sinful’. Put together, the term, “Boko Haram” literally translates thus, ‘Westernization is sinful’, ‘Western education is forbidden’ or ‘Western influence is a sin’. Barna (2014) noted that Boko Haram is the name commonly associated with the organization ‘Jama’atu Ahlis-sunnah Lidda’Awati Wa’l-Jihad’, or ‘the people committed to the propagation of the prophet’s teachings and Jihad’.

There are many barriers to understanding the group, very little information about the organization can be verified; and so solid, dependable information in general is hard to come by in Nigeria. Naturally, questions have been raised about what it has and has not done. Many possible sources of information are unreliable.

Fulani militia

The Fulani militia comes from a nomadic, predominantly tribe. In 2014 the militia group was named the fourth deadliest terrorist group in the world by the Global Terrorism Index. The Fulani herdsmen militia is a pastoralist ethnic group living in the central regions of Nigeria, predominantly in the middle belt. The militias group has clashed with indigenous tribes and local, mainly over grazing land. The atrocities perpetrated by this militia group include the destruction of houses, churches, as well as the seizure of land and properties. Reports also have it that they also kidnap people. Recently, the middle belt part of Nigeria has witnessed killings of innocent Nigerians, mainly farmers. These killings stem from the nefarious activities of the Fulani militia. The activities of this militia group have raised considerable security challenge not only in North central but also in a handful of areas across Nigeria.

While, there is no general acceptable definition of Fulani militia group, however, this study define the group as the socio cultural ethnic group that organized to perpetrate crime in the name of grazing across Nigeria society.

Factors Responsible for Organised Criminal Group's Formation in Nigeria

Organised criminal groups in Nigeria before 1990s was not pronounced are rarely mentioned in the trend of crime Obarisiagbon and Aderinto, (2018). However, the current trend of organised criminal groups' activities in Nigeria could be trace to February 25 2000 with the abduction of oil company employee in the Niger Delta region to express their grievances, exploitation and underdevelopment Akpan in Yusuf and Abdullahi, (2020).

Organized criminal group are complex phenomena influenced by various factors, some key factors contributing to their existence and persistence include:

Poverty and inequality: economic disparities can drive individuals to engage in organised crime as a means of survival or to improve their financial situation.

Corruption and lack of economic opportunities: in environments with limited economic opportunities and corrupt institution, organised crime can thrive.

Social exclusion and marginalization: groups or individuals who feel excluded or marginalized may turn to organized crime as a way to gain power, status, or revenge.

Weak governance and law enforcement: in areas with weak or corrupt law enforcement, organized crime can flourish.

Conflict and instability: organised crime often thrives in environments with conflict, instability or weak institutions.

Advancement in technology: the rise of technology has enabled organized crime groups to operate more efficiently, communicate securely and access new markets.

Effect of organised criminal groups activities on social life in Nasarawa state

In the explanation of the State Governor, Engr. Abdulahi Sule, the successful influx of unknown Fulani herdsmen and strangers from the forests of Ondo and Oyo State into local communities in Nasarawa State has made dislodged Boko Haram members from the North-East part of the country and the Darussalam group from Niger State to join them. Daily Trust, 30th August, (2020)

In 2022, the abduction of school children has been reported in the State in LGEA primary school Nasarawa (Attah, 2021). On 21st May, 2022, the chairman of Keffi LGA and his driver were kidnapped, while his orderly, Alhasan Habeeb, was killed during the attack. On January 23, 2021, Sahara Reporters informed Nigeria about the killing of nine Soldiers in Doma LGA by Boko Haram while on a rescue operation in the forest along Mararaba Udege road. Sahara, (Jan, 23, 2021).

The Uttu/Kenyehu forest and the contiguous hills in Nasarawa Toto are regarded as the most dangerous forest in Nasarawa State (Olaniyi, 2021). The adjoining communities of Bakonk, Kabusu, Panda, Banshabiyar, Amkaba and Gidaurai, all in Nasarawa Toto, Karu and Wamba LGAS are farming communities that have been infiltrated by Boko Haram members. Other communities where the terrorist organised criminal groups have been sighted are Mararaba, Udege in Tunga and Loko area, Gudi/Marao and Ambaka in Farun Ruwa Development area and Umasha/Gadabuke in Nasarawa Toto area. Olaniyi, (2021).

Findings reveal that organised criminal groups activities has affected social life activities in the aspects of attending social functions such as marriage ceremony, religion activities, visit to relative, social gathering and so on and so forth. People are afraid to move around freely in the community because of the fear of being kidnap by bandit. (Field work, PhD, 2025)

Elsewhere, Nigerians in trouble communities have responded in several ways to the organised criminal groups that invade their communities. One method of response has been to set up vigilante group to defend themselves, (Crisis Camp, 2016). The second methods have been to comply with the demand of the organised criminal gang and supply them information in order to guarantee their own safety.

The third method consists of relocating and /or running away from the community. With the acquisition of sophisticated weapons, organised criminal groups not only invade and terrorize the communities; they wreak havoc as community members are forced to pay local taxes and protection fees either through giving their farm produce or selling the products and ray cash in order to stay alive. Crisis Camp, (2016).

While crimes and the organised criminal groups are local, the State relies on Nigeria's centralized approach to security. The Nigeria police, the DSS and the Military special force at Doma respond to the atrocities of the criminal gang occasionally. In spite of this periodic response by the security agencies, the local communities in the State are suffering under the activities of the Boko Haram, banditry and Fulani militia organised criminal gangs. The gangs operation appears to have devastating impact on social life of people in these communities in the State.

Boko Haram like other extremist groups have launched irregular warfare on the Nigerian State and her neighbours in the Lake Chad Basin resulting in countless loss of lives, property and displacements in addition to a heated polity raising safety concerns for Nigeria and her neighbours. Amalu (2015) examined the threats of Boko Haram insurgency on human security in Nigeria revealing that insurgency has claimed a lot of lives and property; compounded the food and nutrition insecurity situation in the country; aided the spread of infectious diseases; denied millions of children and youths access to education; increased the number of internally displaced persons with dire need of shelter and has caused people to live in constant fear and anxiety. Amalu (2015) concludes that Boko Haram Insurgency has negative impact on human security; noting that, counter-insurgency can only be effective when issues of poverty, corruption and bad governance are effectively addressed. Concurrently, Mohammed, (2020). Argued that Boko Haram terrorist attacks evidenced by abduction and killing of people; destruction of homes, classrooms, health centers, churches, mosques, and farms has plunged the nation into a persistent state of insecurity. The Boko Haram insurgency has threatened the basics of food, safety, shelter, education and defence which primarily constitute security for the human person; thus, constituting a threat to human security.

Alhaji and Ahmad, (2018) found that Boko Haram insurgency has amplified the number of IDPs in the country, making it one of the highest IDP populations in Africa. They noted that several women and children have been psychologically traumatized by the activities of Boko Haram along with the abuse of power by the military, police, and civilian Joint Task Force (JTF).

As corroborated by other scholars noted, these negative experiences such as gruesomely losing a parent, child or relative paves the way for a myriad of real life challenges including child abuse, rape, trauma, etc. among others which take a huge toll on the individuals affected, particularly women and children. The case of trauma as a result of stigmatization is noted by Bloom and Hilary, (2016) where women and girls hitherto in the captivity of Boko Haram escaped and successfully make it home, only to be greeted with stigmatization and considered unworthy of marriage as families and communities prove unwilling to receive them. Hence, providing fodder for the Boko Haram sect in terms of ready lieutenants to perpetrate violent crimes in Nigeria. Thus, those adversely affected by Boko Haram insurgency may engage in social vices to fill the vacuum occasioned by the insurgency leading to the grooming of irresponsible members of society who will in turn pose an existential threat to their immediate environment and the larger society if left unchecked.

THEORITICAL FRAMEWORK

Relative deprivation theory

This theory was developed by Radzinowicz and King in 1997. Relative deprivation refers to a feeling of deprivation which a group or an individual experience when its/his expectations are not met or when a group or person feels deprived in comparison to other similar group or persons. The basic tenet of the theory is that people who are deprived of things they valued be it money, justice, status or opportunity and privilege in society may join social movement with the hope of redressing their grievances. Relative deprivation theory refers to the idea that feeling of deprivation and discontents are

related to a desire point of reference (reference group). Relative deprivation is generally considered to be the central variable in the explanation of social movements and is used to explain the quest for social change that inspires social movement. Social movements, therefore, emerge from collective feeling of relative deprivation. Lee and Young (1994) opined that deprived youths are usually pushed to the edges in any given society. In response to their social, monetary and political deprivations, greater number of youth have momentarily entered the world of violence and created violence sub-culture.

Also Gurr (1970) maintained that the perception of deprivation, marginalization and persecution of individuals in a given community may lead to frustration and anger. The assumptions of relative deprivation theory are relevant to the understanding of Boko Haram Fulani militia organised criminal group and banditry in Nigeria and Nasarawa state in particular. From the theory, it can be argued that youths who felt deprived of what they supposed to have, such as employment opportunity, good governance, quality education and so on and so forth resort to violence through organised criminal activities.

CONCLUSION

The concern of this paper is to examine the effects of organized criminal groups' activities on social life in Nasarawa State Nigeria. The paper established that organised criminal group activities affects social life in the areas of economic, political, education, religion, social as well as psychological activities in the State.

However, the paper recommended that the scenario need to be checked, government should address the root factors that give birth to organised criminal groups, government should beef up security to control the activities of organized criminal groups, the welfare of citizens should be taken seriously to discourage people from forming and joining organised criminal groups. Politician should stop hiring youths to use them as thugs for their selfish gain in the society.

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